

**BALALAR OYINLARI BOLGAN AWELEMEN – DUWELEMEN HAM
SHAQSHAGALA, SHAGALA QOSIGI HAQQIDA**

Solaeva Xosila

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“Folklor hám etnografiya” qaniygeligi sırtqı bólim 2-kurs studentı

Moyanov Iqlasbay Jiyenbaevich

dotcent, PhD

Ózbekistan mámleketlik kórkem óner hám mádeniyat instituti Nókis filyali

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Annotaciya. Bul maqalada balalar oyını bolğan áwelemen-dúwelemen hámde shaqshagala, shaqshagala qosıgı haqqında sóz etilgen.

Gilt sózi: Folklor, balalar, shıǵarma, muzıka, oyın, qosıq, áwelemen-dúwelemen, shaqshagala, shaqshagala.

**AUELEMEN – DUELEMEN, CHILDREN'S GAMES, AND ABOUT THE SONG
SHAHSHAGALA, SHAGALA**

Abstract. This article tells about auelemen-duelemen, a children's game, as well as about the song of shahshagal, chagall, the song about gravel.

Key word: folklore, children, artwork, music, dance, song, auelemen –duelemen, shahshagala, chagala.

**AUELEMEN – DUELEMEN, ДЕТСКИЕ ИГРЫ, И ПРО ПЕСЕНКУ ШАХШАГАЛА,
ШАГАЛА**

Аннотация. В этой статье рассказывается о аueleмен-дуелемен, детской игре, а также о песне шахшагала, шагала песне о гравии.

Ключевое слово: фольклор, дети, художественное произведение, музыка, танец, песня, аueleмен –дуелемен, шахшагала, шагала.

Balalardıń qızıq oyını – “Áwelemen – dúwelemen” oyını. Onı oynaw ushın balalar aylana dógerek otırıp, ortaǵa ayaqların shıǵarıp, bir – birine tiygizip qalasıwı kerek. Balalardıń ishinen úlkenirek birewi:

Áwelemen – dúwelemen,
Salqan iyttiń sanı menen,
Qara qoydıń qanı menen,
- Áwez bala qayda ketti?

- Duzğa ketti.

- Qashan keler?

- Jaz keler?

Jaz ikelmese

Gúz keler.

Pállempish

Oyğa tús.

Sen tur,

Sen shıq! - dep aytadı.

Sol eń sońǵı „sen shıq“ sózi tuwrı kelip ayılǵan bala ayaǵın oyınnan shıǵaradı. Ol utılǵan bolıp esaplanadı. Usı tártip penen qaytalanıp aytıla beredi. „Sen shıq“ sózi kelgen bala oyınnan shıǵıp qala beredi. Eń sońında bir bala shıqpay qaladı. sol bala utqan bolıp esaplanadı. Balalar bul oyındı júdá ıqlaslanıp, úlken qızıǵıwshılıq penen oynaydı. Sanawdıń tártibin buzdırmay, qattı talap etip otradı. Buzsa, balalar óz ara dawlasıp qaytadan sanatadı. Bul oyın balanı sanawǵa úyretedi, olardıń ruwxın kóteredi, waqıtın kewilli ótkeredi. balalar ayaq oyının oynaw ushın „shaqshaǵala, shaǵala“ qosıǵın paydalanadı. Bul oyınnıń tártibi, balalar aylana dógerek bolıp turadı da, birewin ortaǵa shıǵaradı.

Shaq shaǵala, shaǵala

Kóldiń boyın jaǵala,

Uzın suwda balıq bar,

Alalmaysañ shaǵala, -

dep balalar xor bolıp birgelikte qosılıp, qol shapalaqlap qaǵısıp ayta baslaydı. Ortadaǵı bala „shaǵala“ oyının dawam etedi. Ortaǵa qol oramal tastalınadı. Onı oyınshı bala shaǵala suwan balıq alǵanday etip, tislep alıwı kerek. Bul oyın balanı shaqqanlıqqa, úyretedi. Sap deneli, shınıqqan bolıp ósiwine járdemlesedi.

Xalıq arasında milliy saz ásbapları tuwralı bahalı dáreklerdiń saqlanıp qalǵanlıǵı, ásirese, onıń balalar folklorınıń túrli janlarında ushırasatuǵılıǵı, usı máseleni tereńirek úyreniw zárúrligin kóldeneń qoyadı.

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